

QUIZ

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PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice

QUIZ: MY SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The starting point of an academic essay is the researcher's initial response to the topic or question. This response is based on what the researcher already knows. What should the researcher do next?**
 - The researcher needs to carry out the research, question the response and find some answers.¹**
 - The researcher needs to formulate discussion groups.
 - The researcher needs to start thinking about the conclusion of the research.
 - Carry out a complete check of the references and bibliography.

¹ Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed 11/5/2020), 2015, 1.

2. **Most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing. Researchers are advised to put their essays aside for a few days after writing it before they begin to edit it. What benefit does this have?**
- This gives the researcher the ability to question the work and look for faults.
 - Allows time to check the work for plagiarism and quotations.
 - This gives the researcher time to think further about the answer and arguments and return to the work with a fresh perspective.²**
 - The researcher may not be happy with the outcome of the work and want to start again.
3. **Evidence used in research was provided by previous researchers who used evidence provided by their predecessors and is a process that has gone on for years. How does Turabian describe this transfer of information?**
- Lending to other researchers.
 - Benefiting from the research of others.³**
 - Using ideas that others have also used.
 - Benefiting from those who have not benefited from others.
4. **According to Turabian the structure of research is very much dependent on the area of research. What is the structure used in experimental sciences?**

² EUCLID, 3.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press. 2018), 5.

- Conclusion, Methods and Materials, Results, Discussion, Introduction.
 - Discussion, Results, Introduction, Conclusion, Methods and Materials.
 - Methods and Materials, Conclusion, Discussion, Introduction, Results.
 - Introduction, Methods and Materials, Results, Discussion, Conclusion.**⁴
5. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe a qualitative dissertation is not a linear process but one that involves reading, planning, writing, conduction study, collecting and managing data, analysing data and reporting findings and what other aspects?**
- Interpreting and synthesising findings, developing conclusions and recommendations.**⁵
 - Talking to the participants of the research if this be required.
 - Knowing the difference between a qualitative dissertation and a quantitative dissertation.
 - Making sure that you are able to complete the dissertation before you start it.
6. **Bloomberg and Volpe are very clear on the purpose of defending a qualitative dissertation being two-fold the first reason is to publicly discuss the research and what has been discovered in the process and the second reason is?**

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 67.

⁵ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 1.

- To have an informal discussion with your instructor and members of the defence committee.
- To evaluate the acceptability of the study as a scholarly piece of research.⁶**
- To be recognised for all the hard work put into producing the dissertation.
- To produce a piece of work that can help others.

7. **What does the World Health Organisation (WHO) attribute to be important in identifying its house style?**

- A preferred spelling, punctuation, terminology and formatting.⁷**
- A preferred use of British or American English as long as there is indication as to which is being used.
- A preferred use of punctuation only as it is an important criteria.
- A preferred spelling, punctuation and formatting only.

8. **What are some of the advantages of using the WHO house style?**

- The end product has consistency only.
- The end product is a unified finished product only.
- The end product is streamlined and efficient, unified and consistent.⁸**
- The end product is polished and sophisticated.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 172.

⁷ WHO *Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organisation. 2004, 1.

⁸ WHO, 1.

9. **What is Larviciding?**

- Larviciding is the process of controlling mosquitoes when they are in the larval form as a means of eradicating malaria.⁹**
- It is a method used to increase the population of mosquitoes.
- It is the method used to control mosquito numbers when they are in the adult form.
- It is the spraying of mosquito nets as a means of killing mosquitoes.

10. **What role does malaria play in making the host susceptible to some bacterial infections?**

- Malaria attacks the host's immunity and can render them susceptible to all bacterial infections.
- Malaria attacks the host's immunity and can render them susceptible to some bacterial infections.¹⁰**
- Malaria improves the host's immunity and can render them resistant to some bacterial infections.
- Malaria improves the host's immunity can make them resistant to all bacterial infections.

⁹ Mathieu Maheu-Giroux, *Malaria Vector Control in Sub-Saharan Africa: Impact and Economic Evaluation of Larviciding*. Doctoral dissertation, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, 2015.

¹⁰ Justin Cunnington, Aubrey, *Malaria and susceptibility to other infections*. PhD thesis, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine, 2012.

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